

VOLUME - 1
ISSUE - 7

ISSN | 2321-4872
FEBRUARY '2014

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES AND RESEARCH

AN INTERNATIONALLY APPROVED AND MONTHLY PEER REVIEWED MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Chief Editor
Dr. N.V.S. Suryanarayana

Invited Articles from: Academicians, Consultants, Management Practitioners, NGOs, Field Workers etc. on different facets of Science and Humanities viz. Physics, Chemistry, Geo-physics, Botany, Zoology, Fisheries, Marine Science, Engineering and Computer Science, Instrumentation, Mathematics, Bio-Chemistry, Bio-technology, Food and Nutrition, Occupational Health, Medical, Para-medical, Alternative Medicine, Nursing, Home Science, Hotel Management, Anthropology, Education, Special Education, Adult Education, Distance Education, Geology, Psychology and Para Psychology, History, Geography, Legal Studies, Language and Literature, Philosophy & Religious Studies, Sociology, Economics, Political Science and Public Administration, Marketing, Rural Development, Commerce & Management Studies, Corporate Governance, Business, Human Resource Development, Corporate Social Responsibility, Social Work, Applied Research, Art & Craft Education, Journalism and Mass Communication, Social Exclusion and Inclusion, Library Science, Women Studies etc.,

WESTWIND PUBLISHING HOUSE
FLAT NO 109/8, ANITHA NAGAR, LOWKHANDWALA COMPLEX,
KHANDAVILLI EAST, MUMBAI, MAHARASTRA, INDIA

FOR SUBSCRIPTION OF ARTICLES AND QUERIES:

DR. N.V.S. SURYANARAYANA

CHIEF EDITOR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES AND RESEARCH (IJMSR)

DOOR NO. 19-5-5, KANUKURTHIVARI STREET,

VIZIANAGARAM - 535002, ANDHRA PRADESH, INDIA

E-MAIL: ijmsr09@gmail.com, westwind786@yahoo.com

PHONE: 09666633885, 09440348609

ISSN 2321-4872

**PECKING ORDER AND TRADE-OFF THEORIES OF CAPITAL STRUCTURE
IN STEEL AUTHORITY OF INDIA LIMITED AND TATA STEEL LIMITED:
AN IMPLEMENTATION AND ANALYSIS**

***DR. P. SANJEEVI**

ABSTRACT:

This paper tests traditional capital structure models against the alternative of a pecking order model of corporate financing of two leading steel companies which are SAIL and TSL. The basic pecking order model, which predicts external debt financing driven by the internal financial deficit, has much greater time series explanatory power than a static tradeoff model, which predicts that each firm adjusts gradually toward an optimal debt ratio. Since bankruptcy capital cost and firm value, they should be taken into account at least as much as tax advantage provided by the loan for establishing capital structure. We show that our tests have the power to reject the pecking order against alternative tradeoff hypotheses and tried to form a frame for capital structure at first and then mentioned about trade-off and pecking order theories on establishing capital structure. In the last part, a research, relating to the importance of factors which are taken into account while establishing capital structure in SAIL and TSL, was applied, and analyses regarding the determination of current situation of active present organizations were done.

KEYWORDS: *Capital Structure, Bankruptcy, Agency Costs, Pecking Order Theory, Trade-off Theory*

INTRODUCTION:

A great deal of theoretical and empirical studies made on forming capital structure of business organizations indicates that the issue is one of the most discussed ones in finance literature. A business organization needs certain amount of capital to be established and maintained. The discussions, arising from forming capital structure which represents division of business organization's total capital requirement between equity capital and debt, are based on capital structure theories of Modigliani-Miller in general. The studies done on the issue has brought about discussions arising from two different approaches on whether is it possible to achieve optimal capital structure through changing capital structure of business organizations and thus whether it can change average capital cost and firm value. While one of the approaches is claiming that the level of debt use in business organizations affects enterprise risk, expected income, average capital cost and so its enterprise value, the other is arguing that the decisions relevant to capital structure of business organizations are independent from enterprise value and average capital cost.

We examine the cost considerations, those are very much influence of corporate and personal taxes, agency costs, information asymmetry and bankruptcy costs exist, the irrelevance of the capital structure for a firm's value is an inappropriate generalization. The value of the levered firm would therefore be equal to that of the unlevered firm plus the value of the debt tax shield. This would mean that firms, which have higher tax benefits, *ceteris paribus*, should have higher leverage. However, the study overestimates the benefits of using debt, as this would imply that an optimum capital structure would consist almost entirely of debt financing, with no limits to the maximum amount of debt a firm can safely employ. Moreover, the theory rests on similar assumptions as the irrelevance proposition including no personal taxes, potential bankruptcy costs, information asymmetry and agency costs in this choice of debt.

APPLICABILITY OF THE TRADE-OFF THEORY AND PECKING ORDER THEORY;

It is one of the most known theories on company financing the theory, pioneered by Myers (1984), refers to manager's preferences in finding out sources to meet finance need. According to the theory, business managers prefer internal financing by means of borrowing. Modigliani and Miller's (1958) approach making study on the capital structure evoked great interest in researchers all over the world that led to the emergence of two broad theories viz tradeoff and pecking order theory.

Trade off theory: This theory says that there is a trade-off between interest tax shield and financial distress costs. This trade-off gives a target debt ratio for each firm.

Value of the Levered Firm = Value If All Equity Financed + PV of interest tax shield - PV of Financial Distress Cost.

Figure 1: Optimal Capital Structure in Trade-off Theory

PECKING ORDER THEORY:

This theory was discussed by Myers and Majluf (1984). It is mainly based on the information asymmetry. It says that the managers (insiders) have more information than investors (outsiders) about their company's future prospects and value. The companies use in this information as an indicator to signal the outsiders about a company's future prospects. For example a company may increase its dividend from that of the previous year. This indicates that the company has good future prospects. It has an impact on the selection of sources of financing the business. On the basis of preference for sources of financing, this theory suggests an order followed by companies, which are internal source, debt financing, hybrid securities and new issue of equity shares. According to the pecking order theory, argued by Myers in 1984, the sources to be used to meet financing need of organizations are ordered as follows

- 1) Business organizations prefer to finance with equity at first hand.
- 2) Dividend rates of them are determined in comply with investment opportunities.
- 3) The cash flow as a result of fluctuations occurred during profitability of organizations may be more or less than expenditures made for investment. As a result of this, the business organization can perform two different operations such as dragging down security portfolio or increasing the ratio of dividend payment.

4) If equities are inadequate and if there is a need for external sources, the organization prefers to issue bond at first, then convertible bond in need, and shares finally. Except for costs of asymmetric information in the market. Under evaluation of issued shares of the organization by the market may require retreat in evaluation of investments with positive net current value.

In present paper, an attempt is made to examine the applicability of these two theories for the Steel Authority of India Limited and Tata Steel Limited to identify the relationship between explanatory variables of capital structure and leverage.

TRADEOFF THEORY:

Many studies are proposing the advantages of tax shields suggest that firms can employ infinite levels of debt. However, subsequent studies argue that such conclusions are unrealistic and can have little intuitive appeal because for firms, there might be risks associated with acquiring and servicing debt.

Figure 2: Firm Value with Tax Advantage and Bankruptcy Cost

As a result, a bankruptcy without costs would not change the value of the firm. In this regard the following reviews are stated below:

Peterson 1994, in this study, explained that the firm value in business organizations is affected from tax advantage provided by borrowing interest and from bankruptcy costs arising from borrowing. If the leverage level of business organization has been increased (borrowing more than equity financing) the firm value rises. Concordantly, an increase in direct and indirect bankruptcy costs by borrowing will decrease firm value. Therefore, it is extremely important to have a balance between tax advantage and bankruptcy risks.

Myers (2001) in this study explained that the main aim is to examine the interest tax benefits on debt. He indicated that the trade-off theory is intrinsically contradictory on the tax issue as it implies that profit-maximizing firms, with excellent credit ratings, would prefer to have high debt interest tax shields, which is not always the case. As a matter of fact, studies by Myers (1984, 2001).

In this study, another argument of Capital Structure, which has been propounded by Frank and Goyal (2007), supported the trade-off theory that the most reliable factors in the leverage decisions of the publically traded American firms are median industry leverage, market-to-book ratio, tangibility, profits, log of assets and expected inflation.

A modified version of the Tradeoff theory described by Berkowitz and Udell (2010) in this study Traditional tradeoff models of Capital Structure contend that firms weigh the tax benefits with the potential distress costs associated with debt financing to arrive at an optimal or target Capital Structure. In this model and economy in which firms consider the opportunity cost that accompanies debt capacity is limited in their model so the decision to issue debt financing today decreases a firm's ability to borrow in the future. This option to preserve debt capacity is valuable to firms.

We try to know the importance of asymmetry information and signaling theories for optimum Capital Structure of the firm. The pecking order theory and the financial growth or the cycle model of capital structure have been forwarded to explain how firms make their capital structure decisions. These theories are based on asymmetric information and signaling theories, under which firm managers are assumed to have greater information on the future prospects of the firm as regards future revenues and investment opportunities than outside investors.

Bhaduri (2002), studied the factors affecting Capital Structure in the Indian corporate sector. It is supposed that an older company has a higher level of information transparency. This same research uses variable dividend yield that tests signal theory according to which this variable has a negative influence. It is also possible to add factors of the company's uniqueness such as a percentage of R&D in sales or percentage of advertisement expenses in sales. Bhaduri, who develop a model that account for the possibility of restructuring costs in attaining an optimal Capital Structure and address the measurement's problem that arises due to the unobservable nature of attributes influencing the optimal Capital Structure and found that optimal Capital Structure choice can be influenced by factors such as growth, Cash flow, size, product and industry characteristics and also conform the existence of restructuring costs in attaining an optimal Capital Structure.

Leary & Roberts (2004) stated that the conventional view of the Pecking Order Hypothesis of Myers and Majluf (1984) is that companies have a preference ranking over securities because of information asymmetry between the companies' well informed managers and their less informed investors. Managers use their informational advantages to issue securities when they are overvalued. However, investors aware of management's incentives will discount the price that they are willing to pay for the securities. This will result in underinvestment problems and managers will forgo some profitable investments opportunities because managers cannot convey their private information to the investors.

AIM OF THE RESEARCH:

The aim of this research is to determine the approach adopted by SAIL and TSL operating in steel sector while establishing their capital structure, and to set significant level of factors and applicable modern capital structure theories, which they consider while using external sources.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES:

- Main objectives of the Paper is as follows
- To study and analyze the capital structure determinants of Steel Authority of India Limited and Tata Steel Limited.
- To review the importance of trade-off theory and pecking theory.

To examine the applicability of Trade-off and Pecking order theories for the Steel Authority of India Limited and Tata Steel Limited.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

- For analyzing the objectives of the study, the following null hypotheses is to be tested:
- H₀: There is no impact between Total Debt and Capital Structure Determinants of Steel Authority of India Limited and Tata Steel Limited.
- H₀: There is no impact between the Long term Debt and Capital Structure Determinants of Steel Authority of India Limited and Tata Steel Limited.
- H₀: There is no impact of Trade-off theory and Pecking order theory on capital structure (TD and LD) of SAIL.
- H₀: There is no impact of Trade-off and Pecking order theory on capital structure (TD and LD) of TSL.

METHODOLOGY:

The design of the present study is descriptive and analytical in nature to cover the period of 10 years from 2004 to 2013. The data which is required for the analysis and that could fulfill our objectives that have been collected mainly from two sources, viz 1) primary and 2) secondary data.

Primary data was collected from the officials and other employees through interviews and discussions regarding different aspects of the SAIL and TSL.

The study was also based on the secondary data obtained from the audited balance sheets and profit & loss accounts, operational reports, budgets, manuals and also the annual reports of SAIL and TSL. Besides, the facts, figures and findings advanced in similar earlier studies and the Annual and Financial Reports and Government publications are also used to supplement the secondary data.

For assessing the behavior of data statistical techniques have been used such as descriptive, correlation, Regression, t-test, skewness, and kurtosis are used for this study. For these statistical measures are calculated by using SPSS soft ware.

TESTING AND APPLICABILITY OF THE TRADE-OFF THEORY AND PECKING ORDER THEORY TO THE SAIL AND TSL:

Testing of Hypotheses: In this paper researcher made two hypotheses to know that the applicability of the Trade-off Theory and Pecking order Theory to the capital structure of SAIL and TSL. It was applied Regression analysis for computing the appropriate β values and used ANOVA, tested these two dependent variables i.e. Total Debt and Long term debt and eight independent variable i.e. profitability, tangibility, sale, growth, ICR, liquidity, assets and NDT of the SAIL and TSL. (Used two tailed test) The hypotheses results are re-stated here under:

H₁: There is no impact between Total Debt and Capital Structure determinants of Steel Authority of India Limited and Tata Steel Limited.

TABLE 1 ANOVA TABLE (SAIL)

Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	.158	8	.020	15.445	.194
Residual	.001	1	.001		
Total	.160	9			

a. Predictors: (Constant), liquidity, asset, growth, ICR, profitability, tangibility, sale, NDT
 b. Dependent Variable: Total Debt

TABLE 2 ANOVA TABLE (TSL)

Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1.056	8	.132	28.559	.144
Residual	.005	1	.005		
Total	1.060	9			

a. Predictors: (Constant), liquidity, asset, growth, ICR, profitability, tangibility, sale, NDT
 b. Dependent Variable: Total Debt

Inference: It can be seen from the ANOVA Table 1 & 2, Capital Structures Leverage (TD) and its determinant components of SAIL and TSL. For P-test, it is clear that the computed value is more than critical value at 5% level of significance (.194 and .144). Therefore, null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, it is concluded that there is impact between the Total Debt Leverage and Capital Structure determinants of the both the companies.

H₂: There is no impact between the long term debt and Capital Structure determinants of Steel Authority of India Limited and Tata Steel Limited.

TABLE 3 ANOVA TABLE (SAIL)

Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	.112	8	.014	4.165	.363
Residual	.003	1	.003		
Total	.115	9			

a. Predictors: (Constant), liquidity, asset, growth, ICR, profitability, tangibility, sale, NDT
 b. Dependent Variable: Long term Debt

TABLE 4 ANOVA TABLE (TSL)

Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	.176	8	.022	8.811	.002
Residual	.012	1	.012		
Total	.019	9			

a. Predictors: (Constant), liquidity, asset, growth, ICR, profitability, tangibility, sale, NDT
 b. Dependent Variable: Long term Debt

Inference: It can be seen from the ANOVA Table 3 & 4, Capital Structures Leverage (TD) and its determinant components of SAIL and TSL. For P-test, it is clear that the computed value is more than critical value at 5% level of significance (.363 and .002). Therefore, null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, it is concluded that there is impact between the long term debt leverage and Capital Structure determinants of the both the companies.

H₂: There is no impact of Trade-off theory and Pecking order theory on capital structure (TD and TD) of SAIL.

TABLE 5 Relationship between Explanatory Variables and Leverage of SAIL with Trade-off and Pecking order Theories.

Variables	Trade-off Theory	Pecking Theory	Actual Relationship	Total Debt	Long term Debt
Profitability	Positive	Negative	Negative	-.572	-.571
Tangibility	Positive	No relationship is specified	Positive	.572	.570
Sales Size	Positive	Negative	Positive(TD), Negative(LD)	.35	-.55
Growth	Negative	Positive	Negative	-.20	-.596
ICR	Negative	Positive	Positive	0.903	.902
Liquidity	Positive	Negative	Positive	.31	.132
Assets Size	Negative	No relationship is specified	Positive	.32	1.16
NDT	Positive	Negative	Negative	-.577	-.575

Inference: The actual 'p' coefficients of SAIL with Total Debt and Long term Debt to the present study, along with the expected ones under Trade-off and Pecking order Theories are

summarized in the Table 5. Tangibility, growth, sale size and liquidity are exhibiting the same signs as expected under Trade-off Theory. Profitability, sales size, ICR and NDT are exhibiting the same signs as expected under Pecking order Theory. Tangibility and assets size is not expected to have any specific relation under the Pecking order theory to Long term debt leverage. On the whole, the result of the present study indicates an equal chance for both the theories applicable for Steel Authority of India Limited.

H₄: There is no impact of Trade-off theory and Pecking order theory on capital structure (TD and LD) of TSL.

TABLE-6 : Relationship between Explanatory Variables and Leverage of TSL with Trade-off and Pecking order Theories.

Variables	Expected Relationship	Pecking Order Theory	Actual Relationship	Total Debt	Long term Debt
Profitability	Positive	Negative	Positive	0.012	0.011
Tangibility	Positive	No relationship is specified	Negative	-0.007	-0.001
Sales Size	Positive	Negative	Negative	-0.46	-0.85
Growth	Negative	Positive	Negative	-0.43	-0.44
ICR	Negative	Positive	Negative	-0.19	-0.13
Liquidity	Positive	Negative	Positive	0.60	0.54
Assets Size	Negative	No relationship is specified	Positive	.97	1.24
NDT	Negative	No relationship is specified	Positive	.24	1.04

Source: Computed.

Inference: The actual β coefficients of TSL with Total Debt and Long term Debt to the present study, along with the expected ones under Trade-off and Pecking order Theories are summarized in the Table 6. Probability, growth, ICR and liquidity are exhibiting the same signs as expected under Trade-off Theory. Sale size is only exhibit the same signs as expected under Pecking order Theory. ICR, liquidity, tangibility, assets size and NDT are not expected to have any specific relation under the pecking order theory. On the whole, the result of the present study indicates Trade-off Theory is only applicable to Tata Steel Limited.

CONCLUSION:

The findings of this study contribute towards a better understanding of financing behavior in two steel companies. Hypotheses, based on comparing the relationships between total and long term debt leverage with and eight explanatory variables represent that profitability, growth, tangibility, interest coverage ratio, assets size, liquidity, non debt tax shield and sales size, were developed to test which capital structure theories best to explain these two companies' capital structure. The results suggest that both the static trade-off theory and the pecking order theory are pertinent theories whereas there was little evidence to support the information asymmetry theory.

This paper presents the major findings of the capital structure performance of SAIL and TSL over a period of 10 years from 2004 to 2013. Stated, here under:

It is observed that the Tangibility, growth, sale size and liquidity are exhibiting the same signs as expected under Trade-off Theory. Profitability, sales size, ICR and NDT are exhibiting the same signs as expected under Pecking order Theory. Tangibility and assets size is not expected to have any specific relation under the Pecking order theory to Long term debt leverage. On the whole, the result of the present study indicates an equal chance for both the theories applicable for Steel Authority of India Limited.

It is observed that the Probability, growth, ICR and liquidity are exhibiting the same signs as expected under Trade-off Theory. Sale size only exhibits the same signs as expected under Pecking order Theory. ICR, liquidity, tangibility, assets size and NDT are not expected to have any specific relation under the pecking order theory. On the whole, the result of the present study indicates Trade-off Theory is only applicable to Tata Steel Limited.

It is found that there is impact between the Capital Structure Leverage and Capital Structure determinants of the both SAIL and TSL.

The regression results with explanatory variables of total debt and long term debt leverage as compared to the Trade-off and pecking order theories. It is observed that both the theories are applicable to SAIL, but trade-off theory is applicable to TSL only.

Further, the findings of this study have delivered some insights on the capital structure of these two firms. The issue of capital structure is an important strategic financing decision that firms have to make by applying these two trade-off and pecking order theories. It is therefore important for policy to be directed at improving the information environment, managerial strategy, psychology, human capital and network ties impact on the capital structure. This may, if not monitored by concerned authority properly and timely, invite the crisis in financial sector in future.

REFERENCES:

- Amasaveni, R (2009) 'Impact of Leverage on profitability Aluminium in India,' Indian Journal of Finance, Volume3, Number 11, pp.33-41.
- Angales, L, (1995) what do we know about Capital Structure? Some evidence from international data. Journal of Finance 50, pp.1421-1460.
- Bhat and Ramesh (1980) determinants of financial leverage. Some further evidence, the chartered accounted December issue.
- Bhat, Ramesh Kumar (1980) Determinants of Financial Leverage: Some Further Evidence.
- David Durand (1952) "The cost of debt and equity funds for business", Management of corporate capital. The Free Press, New York.
- Fama, E., and K. French, 2002, Testing the trade-off and pecking order predictions about dividends and debt, *Review of Financial Studies*, 15, 1-33.
- Finance Management and policy - Bhatta, VK; Amol publications Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi - 110 002.
- Financial Management and policy; J.C Ven Horne; prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi.
- Financial Management and policy; J.C Ven Horne; prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi.
- Financial Management - Theory and practice - Prasanna Chandra; Tata Mc Graw Hill Company limited, New Delhi.

- Financial management: Weston and Brigham
- Financial Management; I.M. Pandey, Vikas Publishing House, Allahabad,
- Fundamentals of Financial management - James G. Van Horne; Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi
- Gitman, L.J. "Principles of Management of Finance"; New York; Harper & Row Publishers Inc. 1976, p.04.
- G.Poster, Financial Statement Analysis, 3rd ed, Prentice-Hall Inc, 1990.
- Johnson, R.W, "Financial Management", Allyn and Bacon, Boston, 1971, p.227.
- Johnson, R.L, "Financial Decision Making", Good Year, 1973.
- Khan M.Y. and P.K Jain., Financial Management - Text and Problems, Tata Mc Graw Hill publications, New Delhi.
- I.M. Pandey (1984) Capital Structure and Cost of Capital 1 edition, 1984.
- Israel, Ronen, (1992), Capital and ownership structures, and the market for control, Review of Financial Studies 5, 181-198.)
- Strebulaev, I., 2004, "Do tests of capital structure theory mean what they say?" Working Paper, London Business School.
- Annual Reports of SAIL, 2003-2013.
- Annual Reports of TSL, 2003-2013.
- Production Planning Reports of TSL and SAIL.